

Version 2 – April 2023

ENIGMA-OCD Analysis Manual for Task-Based fMRI in HALFpipe

Inhibitory/Executive Domain

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SUMMARY

This manual will take you through the processing steps of the ENIGMA-OCD task-based fMRI analyses in HALFpipe. HALFpipe is a containerized processing pipeline made by [Waller et al. \(2022\)](#) which harmonizes analyses across all ENIGMA-OCD sites. No prior experience with HALFpipe is needed – this manual will cover everything you will need to run pre-processing and first-level analyses in the steps outlined below.

STEP 1: PREPARE FOR DATA ANALYSIS

Gather all data you will need, including anatomical scans, functional scans, event files, and demographic covariates. Ensure that MRI data are fully in BIDS-compliant format.

STEP 2: INSTALL A CONTAINER PLATFORM AND DOWNLOAD THE PROCESSING PIPELINE

You will need either Singularity or Docker to run HALFpipe. The latest version of HALFpipe should be downloaded, even if you have a previous version of HALFpipe.

STEP 3: RUN PROCESSING AND FEATURE EXTRACTION (FIRST LEVEL ANALYSES)

By using the graphical user interface of HALFpipe, you will perform pre-processing according to pre-specified parameters, and will extract first-level contrasts for each subject based on the contrast file that was shared with you alongside this manual.

STEP 4: QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Inspect output of HALFpipe and complete quality assessment in an interactive graphical interface following guidelines provided. Once this is complete, send the HALFpipe output, quality assessments, and covariates back to us, at the latest **by September 1, 2023**.

TROUBLESHOOTING

If you run into problems with any of the steps, refer to the troubleshooting portion of the manual. You can find additional resources on the [GitHub page](#) of HALFpipe, and always get in touch with n.dzinalija@amsterdamumc.nl as a first step when encountering problems.

VIDEO SUPPLEMENT

A video supplement to this manual can be found [here](#):

ENIGMA-OCD Protocols | Task-based fMRI analyses in HALFpipe

Note: The video does not stand alone, it should only be used as an extension to the manual below, but it is particularly intended for new users to navigate the HALFpipe user interface. It will run you through the set-up for analysis, and the steps in the GUI. Note that it also covers group-level analysis, which you **DO NOT** need to perform.

STEP 1: PREPARE FOR DATA ANALYSIS

✓ Ensure you have sufficient disc space

- To run the analysis pipeline outlined in this document, you need a computer with at least 16 gigabytes of RAM and at least 1 GB of free disk space per participant (if not keeping intermediate steps).

Note If running on a personal computer rather than a server or cluster, make sure to use appropriate flags to prevent crashing HALFpipe (see [Troubleshooting 1](#)).

✓ Ensure you have sufficient processing capabilities

- If you are running on a personal computer, supplying multiple cores will speed up processing, but the analysis can also be completed with just one core.
- If you have access to a high-performance computing (HPC) cluster, this will make processing faster and more efficient. This document contains additional instructions to make this as easy as possible for you.

✓ FreeSurfer license

- Preprocessing requires a FreeSurfer license file. These are free, and can be requested with the [FreeSurfer Registration form](#). The license file will be e-mailed to you after you submit the form.

✓ Create an empty directory into which HALFpipe will write all output. Place a copy of your FreeSurfer license file in the working directory.

✓ For each subject you should have the following MRI images available:

- **Raw (non-skull-stripped) 3D T1-weighted (anatomical) image** with .nii or .nii.gz extension. De-faced images are also accepted.
 - **Raw 4D functional (task) image** with .nii or .nii.gz extension (note that you will not be able to use a set of 3D volumes as functional input!). If you have acquired dummy volumes at the start of your scan refer to [Troubleshooting 4](#) below.
 - **Field map images** (if available). Three types are supported:
 - Siemens field maps, consisting of phase and magnitude image pairs.
 - Philips field maps, consisting of one field map image and one or two magnitude images.
 - Blip-up/blip-down field maps, consisting of a pair of EPI images with opposite phase encoding directions (mostly AP and PA).
 - For each, make sure you know the correct meta-data (e.g., echo spacing, echo timing, etc.) belonging to the field map images.
- ✓ Convert data to [BIDS format](#) if not already fully in BIDS-compliant structure
- You can use the BIDS validator at <https://bids-standard.github.io/bids-validator/> to check whether your data is in BIDS format.
- ✓ **Event files** that contain the timing of your tasks. All of the three common formats (SPM MAT, FSL 3-column and BIDS TSV) are supported. Here is an [example BIDS TSV](#) events file.

trial_type	onset	duration
sucGO	8.726	0
sucGO	12.524	0
sucSTOP	57.973	0
sucGO	16.536	0
failSTOP	140.008	0
sucGO	20.135	0
sucGO	23.533	0
sucGO	26.732	0
sucGO	30.331	0
sucGO	33.343	0
sucGO	37.141	0
sucGO	40.54	0

NOTE the headings used here, and that onsets are in **seconds**.

- In case you don't have any of these readily available, here are some resources on how to generate them:
 1. <https://elden.ua.edu/blog/generating-onset-and-duration-mat-file-for-spm-for-fmri-analysis>
 2. <https://andysbrainblog.blogspot.com/2012/07/fsl-tutorial-feat-part-2-reckoning.html>

- Importantly, make sure that the starting time of the events is aligned with the acquisition of the first volume of your task images, unless dummy volumes were acquired at the start of scanning (see [Troubleshooting 4](#)).

- ✓ **Group-level covariates** in a spreadsheet. All common formats (CSV, TSV, XLSX) are supported. Here you can find a [template spreadsheet file](#). You should have the following columns with the column headers:

Subject ID	OCD Diagnosis	(C)Y-BOCS	Age	Sex	Age of onset	Medication status
sub-916002	1	24	22.9	Male	Child	Unmed
sub-916004	1	19	46.05	Female	Child	Unmed
sub-916005	0	0	27.74	Female	HC	HC
sub-916006	1	15	21.75	Male	Adult	Unmed
sub-916007	0	0	28.53	Male	HC	HC
sub-916008	1	29	35.16	Male	Child	Unmed
sub-916010	1	26	50.29	Female	Child	Unmed
sub-916011	0	0	33.13	Male	HC	HC
sub-916012	1	20	47.85	Male	Child	Unmed
sub-916013	0	0	26.06	Female	HC	HC
sub-916014	1	12	46.48	Male	Child	Unmed
sub-916015	0	0	47.83	Female	HC	HC
sub-916017	0	0	38.84	Male	HC	HC
sub-916018	1	24	30.72	Male	Child	Unmed
sub-916019	0	0	38.97	Male	HC	HC
sub-916020	1	23	48.51	Male	Child	Unmed

- Subject ID
 - Identical to the subject ID in the image file name described in section 4, so for example 'sub-020'
 - OCD diagnosis
 - "1" = OCD patient, "0" = healthy control
 - (C)Y-BOCS
 - Y-BOCS or CY-BOCS raw score. Please edit the variable name to include the exact name of the scale used (ex, "Y_BOCS_II")
 - Age (in years)
 - Sex (biological)
 - Male, Female, Other
 - Age of onset
 - "Child" = age of onset age ≤ 17, "Adult" = age of onset 18+, "HC" = healthy control
 - Medication status (at time of scan)
 - "Med" = currently medicated, "Unmed" = currently not taking medication, "HC" = healthy control
- ✓ **1st-level contrast spreadsheet** that was shared with you.
- ✓ Calculate your **high-pass temporal filter** width in seconds.

- For each task condition, calculate the time difference in seconds between the onset of an event/trial/block and the next one of that same condition. Take the maximum time difference across all conditions and all subjects and multiply it by 1.5. If this number is smaller than 125 s, then your high pass filter width is 125 s, otherwise use the larger number as filter width. To find the correct high pass filter width, use [this script](#) once you have converted event files to BIDS TSV format and downloaded the HALPipe container in Step 3 below.

Save the script, then open a terminal window and run the following command:

```
singularity exec halfpipe-latest.sif python \
/path/to/Find_high_pass_filter_width.py /path/to/event/file
```

Make sure to replace `/path/to/Find_high_pass_filter_width.py` with the path to the directory the script is in, `halfpipe-latest.sif` with the full path to the container, and the `/path/to/event/file` with the path to one subject's event file. The script will tell you which high pass filter width to use in Section 7 below.

- If the length of blocks depends on subject performance (adaptive timing) so that your block lengths differ between subjects, please use the maximum value in your sample.
- ✓ Exclude participants with poor/sub-standard performance
- Depending on your task's performance metric (e.g., response accuracy, response timeliness) please exclude any participants that you would exclude for your own analyses. We will soon be in touch about which performance metrics we will use across all sites to exclude poor task performance. However, if you have doubts about any participants, please get in touch with us.

STEP 2: INSTALL A CONTAINER PLATFORM

1. Open a shell/terminal on the computer system where you will be running data processing.
 - Type in `singularity` and press enter. If you see instructions on using Singularity and do not get `command not found`, then you can proceed to the next section. Otherwise, follow the guide at <https://github.com/HALPipe/HALPipe#container-platform> to install Singularity (or Docker for Mac users) without the need for administrator privileges.

IF RUNNING ON AN HPC

Try to run `module load singularity` to see if the administrators provide Singularity as an optional module. You will need to re-run this command every time you log out and back in again, and every time you start working on a node.

- If you get the following error: `The following module(s) are unknown: "singularity"` follow the guide at <https://github.com/HALPipe/HALPipe#container-platform> to install Singularity (or Docker for Mac users) without the need for administrator privileges.
- After installing or loading Singularity, try the command again to make sure that it works.

STEP 3: DOWNLOAD THE PROCESSING PIPELINE (HALPIPE 1.2.2)

1. Download the container image file using one of the following commands:

Container	Version	Command
Singularity	3.0 and above	<code>curl -O https://download.fmri.science/singularity/halfpipe-latest.sif</code>
Singularity	2.x	<code>curl -O https://download.fmri.science/singularity/halfpipe-latest.simg</code>
Docker		<code>docker pull halfpipe/halfpipe:latest</code>

Even if you already have HALPipe installed or have previously used it for processing, please re-download the latest release as bug fixes have been added.

IF USING SINGULARITY

Run `find $(pwd) -maxdepth 1` to show all the files in the current directory (similar to `ls`, but shows the full, absolute path of the files). You should see a file named `halfpipe-latest.sif` listed. This file is the container image that includes all software and code needed for processing.

- ✓ Note down the full path to this file, you will need this later.

IF USING DOCKER

Docker stores the container in its storage base directory. There is no need to remember a file name.

IF RUNNING ON AN HPC

On most HPC clusters, you cannot run jobs in the login (or head) node. Therefore, before launching the pipeline, we recommend that you first request an interactive job, which will allocate you resources to run the job. The commands below are provided for reference, please refer to your HPC's documentation for the exact commands to run, or check with your IT support if you are unsure about these steps.

Job manager	Command
SLURM	<code>srun --time 0-6 --ntasks=1 --pty bash</code>
SGE	<code>qlogin -now no</code>
Torque/PBS	<code>qsub -I -l walltime=12:00:00</code>

Once an interactive session is allocated to you, start the pipeline as follows

```
singularity run --containall --bind /:/ext halfpipe-latest.sif --use-cluster --keep none
```

Make sure to replace `halfpipe-latest.sif` with the path of the file you downloaded in the previous section.

STEP 4: RUN PREPROCESSING AND FEATURE EXTRACTION

NOTE The [video supplement](#) may be particularly helpful for this section.

1. Start the HALPipe container downloaded in the previous step from a terminal window. Please refer to <https://github.com/HALPipe/HALPipe#running> for details and troubleshooting.

Container	Command
Singularity	<code>singularity run --containall --bind /:/ext halfpipe-latest.sif --keep none</code> Replace <code>halfpipe-latest.sif</code> with the path of the file you downloaded in the previous section.
Docker	<code>docker run --interactive --tty --volume /:/ext halfpipe/halfpipe:latest --keep none</code>

You have now opened the user interface, which should look like this:

The user interface will ask you a series of questions about the processing and data. You can always return to previous questions with **Ctrl+C**.

You should run HALPipe once for each sample that you are analyzing, or each scanner that you used. If you are running multiple samples, make sure to do this in separate working directories.

This part of the manual will provide a description of each question:

1. Specify working directory

Navigate to the working directory you created previously by typing in its full path. Suggestions will be displayed below the text box that can be navigated with the arrow keys. Bash-like tab completion also works.

2. Is the data available in BIDS format?

2.1. Yes

2.1.1. Specify the path of the BIDS directory

You can type in the path of the directory just like in step 1. This will automatically load all available images in the BIDS directory, for example: Found 85 T1-weighted image files for 85 subjects and 1 session. Found 85 BOLD image files for 1 sessions, 1 task, and 85 subjects

Check that the number of T1-weighted and BOLD images found matches the data you have. Note that the subject IDs that are extracted from the file names at this stage will be used throughout processing, so they need to match the IDs found in other file names (eg., events file) and the covariate file for analyses to succeed.

3. Check repetition time values

Make sure that all repetition times (TRs) used in your sample are displayed and consistent with the actual values. If you have a sample with different TR's for which you need to make separate adjustments, the sample will need to be split up in sub-cohorts with the same TR (see 2.2.4.).

Note that sometimes a TR of 1 s has been assigned incorrectly in the header of 4D files when these were created by concatenating a set of 3D volumes. If so, manually correct the repetition time.

4. Add more BOLD image files?

Yes if there are additional files that you were unable to add in the previous step, for example because they are stored in a different folder structure or because you want to make separate metadata adjustments to different parts of your sample (e.g. TR).

⇒ Loop back to step 2.

No otherwise

5. Do slice timing?

5.1. **Yes** if you know the slice timing details of the acquisition for your data. If unsure, check with the MR physicist/technician.

In the following steps you will check the slice order and slice timing values. Confirm with **Yes** if they are correct. Otherwise, select **No** and then enter the correct values.

5.2. **No** otherwise

6. Remove initial volumes from scans?

- 6.1. Enter 0, which should be pre-filled. If you believe that your data may require removal of initial volumes, for example due to non-equilibration, you can also enter a different value (first see [Troubleshooting 4](#)).

NOTE removing volumes here will also alter your onsets in the event file, to reflect the volumes that have been removed. So if you instruct HALPipe to discard dummy volumes, be sure that your onset file is synced to the start of dummy scanning, not to the start of the task.

- 6.2. This will automatically load all available field map images in the BIDS directory, for example: Found 160 field map image files for 85 subjects, 1 acquisition, 2 directions, and 1 session. Check that the number of field-map images found matches the data you have.

7. Specify first-level features?

7.1. Yes

For each of the tasks used in your sample separately, you will loop through this and the following steps three times. Each time a different setting is chosen for confound regression for the task, so that we can later assess whether results are independent of the type of confound regression. Each variation in preprocessing settings is represented by a different column in the following table:

PROMPT	VARIATION 1	VARIATION 2	VARIATION 3
Specify the feature type	Task-based	Task-based	Task-based
Specify feature name	ICA_AROMA	MOTION_CORR	NO_CORR
Specify images to use	<i>Only shown if you have multiple tasks in your BIDS directory. Select only the functional images of the task you are currently working on.</i>		
Specify the event file type	<p><i>Only shown if event files are NOT in BIDS convention. Choose the file type of the event files and then enter the path where they are located. If each subject has a unique event file, use the {subject} tag to denote the part of the file name describing the subject. For example:</i></p> <p><code>events/task/sub-{subject}_ses-T0_task-STOP_events.tsv</code></p> <p><i>*Note that 'sub-' remains outside the bracket</i></p> <p><i>For condition files in FSL 3-column format specifically:</i> Use the {condition} tag to denote the part of the file name describing the condition.</p> <p>You should only have to do this once.</p>		
Select conditions to add to the model	You should add every condition that is listed in the contrast spreadsheet we shared with you. Error trials should be modeled in your event files, but no contrasts will be made on these. Do not add any conditions that are not in the spreadsheet.		

Specify contrasts	<p>For each contrast, enter the exact meta-analytical contrast names from the contrast spreadsheet, and carefully fill in the values of the contrast vector as noted in the sheet.</p> <p>On the second and third iterations of the feature specification, you will see the option <code>Use contrasts from existing feature?</code>. You can select <code>ICA_AROMA</code> here.</p>		
Apply a temporal filter to the design matrix?	Enter the high pass filter width you calculated previously for your task.		
Apply smoothing?	<code>Yes</code> , then confirm the default FWHM value of <code>6 mm</code> .		
Specify the filter width in seconds	Enter the high pass filter width you calculated previously. Skip the low pass filter.		
Remove confounds?	Make sure that <code>"ICA-AROMA"</code> is the only option selected	Deselect <code>"ICA-AROMA"</code> and select <code>"Motion parameters"</code>	Deselect all options so that nothing is selected
	You can select and deselect individual options by pressing the space key.		
Do you really want to use inconsistent confounds across features?	-	<code>Yes</code>	<code>Yes</code>
	This confirmation was added to prevent users from accidentally selecting different processing variations without intending to do so. Here we intend to. You should only need to confirm this once.		
Add another feature?	<code>Yes</code>	<code>Yes</code>	<code>No</code>

8. Output a preprocessed image?

8.1. `No`

9. Specify group-level model?

9.1. `No`

HALFpipe will now begin processing. This may take some time.

IF RUNNING ON AN HPC

HALFpipe will now generate and validate the commands to run for preprocessing and analysis. This can take up to a few hours if you have dozens of subjects. Once the program terminates, you should see a file named `submit.slurm.sh` or `submit.pbs.sh` or `submit.sge.sh` in your working directory.

Open this script with your preferred text editor and compare the header lines to an example script in your HPC documentation. If there are any statements that seem to be missing from the generated script (such as specifying a cluster partition), add them.

Finally, submit the script to the HPC queue.

Job manager	Command
SLURM	<code>sbatch submit.slurm.sh</code>
SGE	<code>qsub submit.sge.sh</code>
Torque/PBS	<code>qsub submit.torque.sh</code>

HALFpipe will begin processing immediately. This may take some time.

STEP 5: CHECK PRE-PROCESSING AND PERFORM QUALITY ASSESSMENT

1. Check the `reportpreproc.txt` file in the `reports` folder within the working directory to see whether preprocessing finished. For each successfully processed subject and run you will see the following:

```

sub   task   run   status
-----
276   SPT     1     done
276   SPT     2     done
275   SPT     1     done
275   SPT     2     done
274   SPT     1     done
274   SPT     2     done
273   SPT     1     done
273   SPT     2     done
272   SPT     1     done
272   SPT     2     done
-----

```

For any subjects that did not run correctly, you can try to re-run HALFpipe following the instructions in [Troubleshooting 3](#).

2. Complete the quality assessment manual that is linked at <https://github.com/HALFpipe/HALFpipe#quality-checks>

Please contact me at n.dzinalija@amsterdamumc.nl if you are unsure about a particular image and have not been able to solve the issue with a knowledgeable person (scanner technician/MR physicist/other expert).

3. Export the quality assessment results as described in the quality assessment manual.

You should then have one `exclude.json` file in your working directory. When assessment is done by multiple raters, you need to add a suffix to each file name before the file extension, such as `exclude.2.json` or `exclude.1ea.json`.

IF RUNNING ON AN HPC

Once processing completes, copy the `reports` folder from your working directory to a computer where you can comfortably do quality assessment.

Copy the `reports` folder back to the HALFpipe working directory on the cluster once you have exported the quality assessment results as described in the quality assessment manual.

STEP 6: UPLOAD OUTPUT - DEADLINE: 1ST SEPTEMBER, 2023

4. From within the HALFpipe working directory, compress the 1st-level subject output and quality reports directory.

```
zip --recurse-paths your_site.zip *.txt *.json derivatives/halfpipe reports
```

Replace `your_site` with your site or sample name.

5. Upload the resulting file to [this folder on SURFdrive](#)
 - Password: Enigma-OCD-6202
6. Into the same folder, upload the following files:
 - Covariates file
 - `exclude.json` file
 - We will soon be in touch about other task-specific performance metrics that we would like to analyze.

TROUBLESHOOTING

1. Limiting memory usage and processing power of HALFpipe

If you are running analyses on a single workstation, like a personal computer, or if you are concerned about overloading a shared server (as these analyses are computationally intensive) it is possible to limit the amount of simultaneous processes – also known as threads – running. It is also possible to limit the amount of RAM memory that HALFpipe uses, which is particularly important if running on a single workstation.

To limit threads, add the flag `--nipy-n-procs=X` to the command you used to start HALFpipe, where `X` depends on the number of total threads available. On a shared server this could for example be 6-12. If you don't know how many threads you have available, the safest thing is to set this number to 1. This means it will run a little slower, but there is less chance of a crash.

Use the flag `--nipy-memory-gb X` to limit the amount of memory to just below what you have available on your system. For example, if using the `free -h` command you see that you have 32GB available (under `free`), you could consider limiting `--nipy-memory-gb 22`. For these analyses to run smoothly, this should not be set below 16.

1.1. When HALFpipe exceeds the amount of RAM memory available, you may see an error like this:

```
HALFpipe crash report: "numpy.core._exceptions._ArrayMemoryError: Unable to
allocate 2.47 GiB for an array with shape (307, 1082035) and data type float64"
```

If you see this, use the flag `--nipy-memory-gb` as instructed above.

2. Skull-stripping or normalization appears to have failed for multiple participants

This is particularly common in child samples, and in extreme cases may appear on the quality assessment as in the following examples:

T1w skull stripping

T1w skull stripping

EPI spatial normalization

You can try to fix this by preprocessing the T1-weighted anatomical images prior to re-running HALFpipe on participants who have failed (see [Troubleshooting 3](#))

1) Skull-strip the T1-weighted anatomical images.

1. Download SynthStrip

Container	Command
Singularity	<pre>curl -O https://raw.githubusercontent.com/freesurfer/freesurfer/dev/mri _synthstrip/synthstrip-singularity && chmod +x synthstrip-singularity</pre> <p><i>Or if this doesn't work</i></p> <pre>singularity build synthstrip.sif docker://freesurfer/synthstrip</pre>
Docker	<pre>curl -O https://raw.githubusercontent.com/freesurfer/freesurfer/dev/mri _synthstrip/synthstrip-docker && chmod +x synthstrip-docker</pre>

2. Download [this script for Singularity](#) or [this script for Docker](#).
 - a. Save the script, and edit it as explained in the script notes. Then open a window terminal and run the following commands:

```
cd /path/to/script/directory
```

```
bash Skullstrip_Singularity.csh or bash Skullstrip_Docker.csh
```

Make sure to replace `/path/to/script/directory` with the path to the directory the script is in. The script will skull-strip all T1-weighted images, will rename the original images, and will store them in a folder titled 'Originals' under directory 'anat'.

- 2.1 If running the script produces an "Input image `/path/to/T1_image` not valid" error, this may be caused by specific permissions in Docker or Singularity.

- For Singularity:

You may need to make your disk accessible to Singularity by typing the following command before running the HALFpipe container

```
export SINGULARITY_BIND="/path/to/BIDS/directory/"
```

- For Docker:

If you are working on a Mac, you may need to disable 'Use gRPC FUSE for file sharing' under 'Experimental features' in the Docker Preferences as explained [here](#)

- Once you have executed skull-stripping, go to the working directory and find the `spec.json` file. Open it in a text editor. Find the line that says `"skull_strip_algorithm": "ants"` and change `"ants"` to `"none"`. Save the file.


```

/mnt/scratch-01/anw/nddzinalija/ARRIBA_TIPICCO_rerun/spec.json - nddzinalija@luna.amc.nl - Editor
[Icons] Encoding Color [Settings]
{
  "halfpipe_version": "1.2.2",
  "schema_version": "3.0",
  "timestamp": "2022-07-27_14-55",
  "global_settings": {
    "dummy_scans": 0,
    "slice_timing": true,
    "use_hhr": null,
    "skull_strip_algorithm": "ants",
    "run_mriqc": false,
    "run_fmriprep": true,
    "run_halfpipe": true,
    "fd_thres": 0.5,
    "anat_only": false,
    "write_graph": false,
    "hires": false,
    "run_reconall": false,
    "t2s_coreg": false,
    "medial_surface_nan": false,
    "bold2tlw_dof": 9,
    "fmap_bspline": true,
    "force_syn": false,
    "longitudinal": false,
    "regressors_all_comps": false,
    "regressors_dvars_th": 1.5,
  }
}

```

- In the working directory, delete the folder named `rawdata`
- Start HALPipe as before. After selecting the working directory, HALPipe will detect that the `spec.json` already exists and say `Found spec file in working directory` and ask for the next action. Select `Run without modification`. HALPipe will now begin processing.


```

HALFPPIPE
welcome to ENIGMA HALPipe!
You are using version 1.2.2

Please report any problems or leave suggestions at
https://github.com/HALPipe/HALPipe/issues

Specify working directory
[/scratch/anw/nddzinalija/ARRIBA_TIPICCO_rerun/]

Found spec file in working directory
[Run without modification]
[Start over at beginning]
[Start over at features]
[Add another feature]
[Start over at models]
[Add another model]

```

3. Re-running participants who failed

This command will print any subjects that did not finish processing and write their subject IDs to the text file `subject-list.txt` in your working directory. You need to adjust the paths to your BIDS directory and working directory at the top of the script.

```
#!/bin/bash
BIDSdir=/path/to/BIDS/directory
WORKdir=/path/to/working/directory

cd ${BIDSdir}
ls -d sub-*/ | sed 's:/.*:.' > ${WORKdir}/ALLsubs.txt

cd ${WORKdir}/derivatives/halfpipe
ls -d sub-*/ | sed 's:/.*:.' > ${WORKdir}/PROCsubs.txt

cd ${WORKdir}
while IFS= read -r line; do
  if ! grep -Fxq -- "$line" PROCsubs.txt; then
    echo "$line" >> subject-list.txt
  fi
done < ALLsubs.txt
```

You can also manually edit this file, for example to add new participants that have not yet been processed. Run HALFpipe again with the same command as before, but add the option `--subject-list <full path to text file>` to the end of the command. Then select **Run without modification**.

IF RUNNING ON AN HPC

Edit your submission script to add the option `--subject-list <full path to text file>`, and then submit the job to the HPC queue.

Alternatively, you can also use the option `--subject-include <characters>` to select only one or more subjects. Only subjects with the characters in their subject ID will be run.

4. If you acquired dummy volumes at the start of scanning

It may be possible to remove dummy volumes in HALFpipe during processing, or it may be necessary to remove these volumes manually outside HALFpipe before beginning processing. Which option is suitable for your data depends on how your event files were created. There are two possible scenarios:

Case 1: Your event files are synchronized to the **first dummy volume**

- It is safe to allow HALFpipe to remove dummy volumes (step 4.1 above). HALFpipe will alter the event onsets by subtracting $TR * \# \text{ of dummy volumes}$ from onset times, meaning you don't need to do this manually outside of HALFpipe.

Case 2: Your event files are synchronized to the **first volume of your task images**

- You need to remove dummy scans outside of HALFpipe before starting the container. Otherwise the onsets file will not be aligned with image acquisition. See [this sample script](#) on how this can be done using an FSL command.

5. Error reading field map files

HALFpipe expects accompanying .json files for each field map image. These .json files must have at least the following entries:

```
"TotalReadoutTime": ".01480868658649251212",
"PhaseEncodingDirection": "j",
"IntendedFor": "func/sub-C203_task-SPT_bold.nii.gz"
```

If these fields are missing an error may pop up regarding missing 'Effective echo spacing' or 'Total readout time'.

Total readout time can be calculated if you know the EPI factor and the water-fat shift:

$$\text{Total Readout Time} = \frac{\text{water fat shift}}{434.215} \times \frac{\text{EPI factor}-1}{\text{EPI factor}+1}$$

5.1 Error: "At least one of the EPI runs with alternative phase-encoding blips is missing the required "PhaseEncodingDirection" metadata entry."

This error may occur when loading in field maps that do not have BIDS-compliant naming. For example, this will not work: **sub-001_dir-SPTAP_epi.nii.gz** but this will: **sub-001_dir-AP_epi.nii.gz**

6. Error finding files

If running the HALFpipe container on Singularity/Apptainer (the new name of Singularity), you may get an error like this:

```
"Cannot use "/path/to/your/working/directory/" as a working directory for HALFpipe. Please check that you have sufficient permissions. Please also check that you are using a file system that supports symbolic links."
```

This error occurs if singularity is not able to find the working directory because it is not in its 'bound' paths. When starting up the HALFpipe container, type this instead:

```
singularity run --containall --bind /path/to/your/working/dir halfpipe-latest.sif --keep none
```

Replace **halfpipe-latest.sif** with the path of the file you downloaded, and **/path/to/your/working/dir** with the full path to the directory in which you want output to be stored.

7. Warning phase encoding direction

You may see this warning:

```
[WARNING ] Cannot determine world direction of phase encoding. Orientation: LAS; PE dir: None
```

You can safely ignore this warning if you are not using field maps, or if you are, refer to Troubleshooting 5 above.

